

TIME MANAGEMENT AS A TOOL FOR ORGANIZATIONAL DEVELOPMENT: A CASE STUDY OF SOME SELECTED TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN BAUCHI STATE

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Abstract

This research titled “Time Management as a tool for the organizational development in some selected tertiary institutions in Bauchi state” is to examine how planning and organizing as principles of time management is used in solving the problems of time management. The objective of this study was to examine how effective use of time by management and employees can lead to organizational development. To achieve this objective, four (3) research questions and three hypotheses were formulated; Data were collected from both primary and secondary source judgmental sampling method was used to select some tertiary institutions, in which 50 employees were interviewed via a questionnaire, were utilized, while descriptive statistics, correlation matrix and panel data analysis (Random-effect GLS regression techniques) were utilized as analytical tools in the study with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Also the study is built on the body of literature of time management and organizational development. The finding reveals that, time if properly managed would lead to the development of an organization. Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that proper planning of activities should be done earlier, because the key to effective time management is event control

Keywords: Time, Tool, Management, Organization, Development

Introduction

The effective and efficient use of time is a very vital issue in any organization because the rate of production of employees can be determined by the amount of time they have used in the process of production. Effective time management helps an organization to achieve its aims and objectives. It is very important to know that time management is to be carried out by individuals as persons first before being carried out as employees. Time is known to be man’s most valuable treasure because it waits for no one (Covey, S.R, Merrill, A.R., Merrill, R.R. 2015).

Looking at time from definition by the Webster’s Collins dictionary “it is a period which actions or processes take place. Management can be said to be processed by which an organization directs the actions of its employees towards a common goal or objective. It takes good management for an organization to be successful and profitable, and this success to a great extent depends on the effective use and transition of self and time. Time management can therefore be seen as ways or methods followed to carryout a task effectively and efficiently. Time management is not about working long hours flat out, but it is about

adopting a philosophy of “living life to the full” and not looking at business in isolation. Peter Drucker (1980) said “time is the scarcest resource and unless it is properly managed nothing else can be managed. This is why management views time as an asset. Time management requires systematic approach to managing programmes, activities and schedules, and to achieve this one has to be able to define priorities, avoid procrastination, value time, planning effectively and organizing of activities. It is only if this is done that an organization can be able to achieve its goals and leading to its development. Warren Bennis has referred to organizational development as a response to change, a complex educational strategy intended to change the beliefs, attitudes and structure of an organization so that it can adopt to new challenges, technologies and dizzying rate of change itself., (Merrill, A.R., 2016)

The supply of time is very limited while the demand for it is limitless. Time lost is lost forever; time is life to waste your time is to waste your life. To a typical European, time is money, it must be respected. While to a Nigerian time is a snail, it must crawl and wait for him and no event should take place until two to three hours of advertised take off time and this is one of the major causes of failure in the Nigerian economy. It is therefore imperative that the study of time management in Some selected tertiary institutions in Bauchi state and how it affects the organization’s development cannot be over emphasized. Time management is a major tool upon which the organization can use to achieve its goals and objectives, which in turn leads to organizational development.(Merrill, A.R., 2016).

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Time is a finite commodity and its proper use may lead to increased productivity by a person (Mancihni, 2017), declares that a person’s ability to management their time is one of a key success or failure in a person’s life. One may often wish for more time but one only has 24 hours, 1440 minutes, or 86,400 seconds each day. Since time unlike other resources such as fund, physical information and human resources within some selected tertiary institutions in Bauchi state requires proper management this brings about the need to know that how one uses time depends on skills learned through self-analysis, prioritization, planning evaluation and organizing of tasks considering the prevailing economic crises, inability of the organizations meet their aims and objectives, complex operating environment and increase involvement of management in organizational activities which has left them with little or no time to care for themselves, makes this study on time management an important one. Much like money time is a valuable and limited, and therefore must be protected and use wisely within some selected tertiary institutions in Bauchi state.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the study is to:

- i. To examine how effective time planning and organizing of activities can help in effective use of time of some selected tertiary institutions in Bauchi State.
- ii. To identify some time wastage and how they can be avoided in some selected tertiary institutions in Bauchi State

iii. To suggest ways that management can use in enhancing performance of employees through time management techniques in some selected tertiary institutions in Bauchi State

LITERATURE REVIEW Conceptual Frame work

The term time management is a misnomer because you cannot manage time but rather you manage the events in your life in relation to time. There is no precise definition of time, but scholars have been able to come up with some possible definitions. Webster's Collins defines time as a period during actions or processes take place, and it refers to time as a system or measuring duration.

Healthier (2018) defines time as a scarce resource which must be managed otherwise nothing can be managed.

While Anand (2019) refers to time as the continuum of experience in which events pass from the future through the present to the past. Time from an Islamic point of view is everything in life, and this is so because a Muslim believes he would someday account for his life and how he spent it.

Time is an essential resources, it is irrecoverable, limited and dynamic. Irrecoverable because every minute spent is gone forever, limited because only 24hours exist in a day and dynamic because it is static. It keeps on moving and does not wait for anybody, therefore time must be managed to ensure it is used effectively and efficiently.

Time management is the organization of tasks or events by first estimating how much time a task will take to be completed, when it must be completed and then adjusting events that would interfere with its completion, so that completion is reached in the appropriate amount of time. The deeper study and increased analytical approach to business output has led to an ever growing realization of the importance of the effects of time management. Time management is not about getting more things done in a day, it is about getting the things that matter most done. Time management is the ability to decide what is important in life both at work and even in our personal lives. In essence, you are the one in control of your life and you are the driver of your car(Keith, F and Tahl, R 2019). As a manager there is no other asset at once disposal quite like time, it is a unique asset which must be used judiciously. Time management is an issue which is fundamental to job performance and productivity.

Time is man's most perishable resources Ducker (2018). When money is lost, it can be replaced; if a commodity is lost the factories can reproduce another, but time when lost can never be returned. Time utilization in management essentially means effective planning, prioritizing, scheduling, organizing task, implementing and assessing activities in an organization to ensure goals are achieved. A deeper understanding of the importance of time management and its satisfactory use can lead to the material saving in the economical use of production inputs and results – oriented.

Symptoms and causes of Time Management

A symptom is defined as a sign of indication of something, especially something undesirable. A problem is never agreed to be a problem without the presence of undesirable symptoms. Therefore managing time requires recognizing the symptoms of time mismanagement (Julie, M and Jessi, M 2016).

The major sign of time mismanagement is rushing to cover work load at the end to meet deadlines.

Lawal (1998) identifies some of the main symptoms of time mismanagement as follows:

- i. Missing deadline: This is unable to finish work at appointed time
- ii. Low productivity: This is inability of an organization to meet its expected goal
- iii. Excessive stress: This is as a result of work overloads and work pressures
- iv. Self doubt: pressure and tension on the job
- v. Sleepless night: this will result to lack of concentration on the job
- vi. Exhaustion: to be tired unnecessarily
- vii. Worker longer hours
- viii. Negligence of profunctioness
- ix. Poor quality of output.

.According to William B (2016). To understand the importance of time management, it is important to look at all aspects. By looking at its definition, theories and activities you can gain a clear idea of why time management is so important in your daily life. By understanding the importance of time management, you can improve your life. It's a bold statement but one which has been personally found to be true. You can make your life and work more effective. It doesn't matter if you are an employee or someone senior in a company time management matters.

You can define time management as a set of guidelines, theories and activities that come together to provide a wide range of benefits. This, I think is always the best way to think of time management

Proper time management would yield the following benefits:

- Efficiency of work
- Development of employees
- Elimination of productivity bottleneck
- Increase job satisfaction
- Result in higher return on investment

In conclusion, the first step in improving personal use of time is by recognizing that a problem exist, then one would be able to isolate time wasters and then find a way to tackle the problem by improving planning of daily activities and organizing task, and improve assertiveness skills to achieve results.

Theoretical Framework

This study adopts two important theories as the theoretical framework for the study. The first theory is the theory A, B and C by Alan Lakein which deals with time management aspect of scheduling, while the second is the Pickle Jar theory of time management with the time management aspect of prioritization.

Theory A, B and C

Theory A, B, and C is a management theory propounded by Alan Lakein in 1973 is an organizational management theory that gives a legit time for activities within the organization. According to Lakein there are activities which are “must to do” “should do and “nice to do” A, B and C respectively. Things that fall under “A” which are “Must Do are things that has highest priority in the organization which must be carried out first before considering B and C. in his view activities with highest priority can be categorized into A1, A2, A3 continuously,

Also the “Should Do” which is B’ are activities within or the organization that should be done which are not as important within the “Must Do” which is a and also that are carried out within the organization which is basically of little or no importance within the organization.

In Alan Lakein point of view, until task A is achieved, the organization should not refrain or stop doing it. But where task A is fully achieved, the organization can move to task B, continuously in that order.

The theory A, B and C was developed by Alan Lakein the author of the popular book “How to Get control of your time and your life. It’s a way of prioritizing the items on your to – do list while most of us dump our tasks onto a list without much thought to the weight of each item, the ABC theory makes you categorize tasks as A, B or C

Lakein developed theory A, B, and C to avoid time wasted within the organization, often time management gives task not on priorities but as they appear which is very wrong. ACTIVITIES weight appear not in a chronological order or well arrange manner, it is based on the management decision to carryout activities base on priorities I.E task A, B and C.

METHODOLOGY

The research method adopted in this work is the survey research techniques The study used both qualitative and quantitative method of research. Data were collected through primary and secondary sources. The secondary was collected from annual reports, journals and survey data were obtained from 300 respondents using researcher-designed questionnaire validated by experts and shown to have a reliability coefficient of 0.90. Descriptive and ordinary least square regression statistical techniques were used in analyzing the data with the aid of Statistical package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21..The research study is geographically limited to Bauchi state of Nigeria, and involves the academic staff and non-academic staff of the eleven (11) Public higher institutions in the state, out of which two are universities, two polytechnics, five colleges and two monotechnics. In addition, there is no any private university or polytechnic located in the state.

FINDINGS

At the end of the research, here are the expected outcome:

- i. The most important findings of this research shows that time if properly management would lead to the development of an organization.

- ii. Also the research shows that proper planning and organizing of activities by an organization can lead to achieving its objectives and hence lead to higher productivity and development.
- iii. It has also been observed that most workers in the organization keep time logs and this has helped in minimizing the amount of time that is wasted or mismanaged.

CONCLUSION

Effective time management is a panacea to organizational effectiveness and development. Effective time management will increase the productivity of staffs, it will make the scheduling of tasks easier, it will help staff to prioritize and accomplish important task on time.

Skillful management of time is not superficial but fundamental. Instead of aimlessly allowing external events and pressures control you, make deliberate choices about your use of time. Looking at the analysis from the study, the way to create a life that is consistent with your deepest values and desires is to set priorities, make plans, organize tasks and then make sure to follow through on those plans.

From the data, it is clear that in order to increase productivity and development, workers would have to use certain time management techniques to keep them motivated and on track. Great time management is indeed one of the most vital skills leaders can develop.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Taken from the data analyses that time management is actually a tool for organizational development. It therefore becomes necessary that every person in the organization must treat time very carefully, because nothing affects the bottom lines of an organization more than time effectiveness of its people.

- i. Proper planning of activities should be done earlier, because the key to effective time management is event control. This means that you cannot control your time but you can control what you do with your time
- ii. Management should not always assume that workers know how to manage time, they should make emphasis on the importance of time management not regular meetings and should try to provide the workers with sufficient knowledge on the matter.
- iii. Workers should develop personal planning habits; this should include setting priorities and identifying time wasting activities. This would help to avoid unnecessary task that need no urgent attention.

CONTRIBUTION TO KNOWLEDGE

This study add value to knowledge as stated below

The study explore various forms of utilizing Time Management in some selected tertiary institutions in Bauchi State

- 2. The study explore causes and effects of Time mismanagement in some selected Tertiary institutions in Bauchi State

3. Its provide various strategies to be adopted in utilizing or reducing Time mismanagement in tertiary institutions in Bauchi State

4. This study is concerned with analyzing time management as a tool for organizational development

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